

ABSTRACT BOOK

Bio⁴ Expanding The Horizon

The International Bioscience Conference
and the 9th Joint International
PSU-UNS Bioscience Conference 2024

October 28-29, 2024
Faculty of Science, Prince of Songkla University

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INTRODUCTION

The International Bioscience Conference and the 9th Joint International PSU-UNS Bioscience Conference is a biannual international conference organized by Prince of Songkla University and University of Novi Sad. This year, we are delighted to announce the theme “*Bio4 Expanding the horizon*” to foster knowledge exchange and deepen collaboration during the in-depth discussion session.

The conference will be hosted by Prince of Songkla University at the campus of the Faculty of Science on 28-29 October 2024. We invite experts in the bioscience research field to share and discuss the latest research, innovations, and trends in the field. Holding the event in its own halls enables the Faculty of Science to comply with a more sustainable event management and allows all participants to gain first-hand impressions and explore our facilities. Hat Yai is a vibrant city in southern Thailand, known as the region's educational center, with bustling markets, diverse cultural influences, and serving as a gateway to Malaysia.

Professor Dr. Anchana Prathep

Dean of Faculty of Science, Prince of Songkla University
Chairwoman, 9th Joint International PSU-UNS Bioscience Conference
2024

October 28, 2024

Basic Science Lecture and Laboratory Building 3,
Faculty of Science, Prince of Songkla University

On behalf of the Faculty of Science, Prince of Songkla University, it is an honor to welcome you to the International Bioscience Conference and the 9th Joint International PSU-UNS Bioscience Conference. We extend a warm welcome to our distinguished guests, esteemed speakers, and all participants joining us from various institutions and organizations. Your presence enriches this event, and we are privileged to host you.

This year's theme, *"Bio⁴ Expanding The Horizon,"* reflects our commitment to advancing collaboration and sharing the latest developments in Biology, Biotechnology, Biomedicine, and Bio-sensing Technology. The conference sessions are designed to foster knowledge exchange, and create opportunities for meaningful collaboration across these fields.

We are delighted to present four exceptional keynote speakers: Prof. Dr. Chatchai Muanprasat on Frontiers in Bioscience Research, Asst. Prof. Dr. Sara Bumrungsri on Bioscience Innovations for a Sustainable Tomorrow, Prof. Dr. Snežana Maletić on Organic Soil Amendments, and Assoc. Prof. Dr. Surapong Chatpun on Staff Exchange in the Horizon Europe Framework. Invited speakers will further enrich the program with discussions on topics from medicinal plants to nanomaterials, as well as insights into funded collaborative opportunities.

This year, IBSC is being held in Hat Yai, and for the first time, we are hosting such an international gathering at our faculty. With over 150 participants from six countries—Bangladesh, Czech Republic, Italy, Malaysia, Serbia, and Thailand—this event represents a shared dedication to tackling global challenges in bioscience.

This conference is a reality thanks to our partners and the efforts of our organizing committee, and we are proud to host it as a sustainable initiative focused on reducing our carbon footprint.

We encourage all participants to fully engage, connect, and explore new opportunities over these two days. May this conference inspire ideas and foster enduring partnerships. Thank you, and welcome to the International Bioscience Conference 2024.

Asst. Prof. Dr. Niwat Keawpradup

President of Prince of Songkla University
9th Joint International PSU-UNS Bioscience Conference 2024
October 28, 2024
Basic Science Lecture and Laboratory Building,
Room BSc3, Faculty of Science,
Prince of Songkla University

Distinguished guests, dear colleagues, and participants,

On behalf of Prince of Songkla University, we are delighted to welcome all distinguished guests, colleagues, and participants to the 9th Joint International PSU-UNS Bioscience Conference. This event unites us in the pursuit of knowledge and innovation in bioscience, underscoring the strong collaboration between Prince of Songkla University and the University of Novi Sad.

The conference theme, *“Bio⁴ Expanding The Horizon,”* invites us to deepen our understanding across areas such as environmental science, biotechnology, and health. It is inspiring to see researchers, academics, and students from six countries—long-standing partners and friends of PSU—gather to explore these critical topics.

I extend my gratitude to the Faculty of Science for organizing this low-carbon event, demonstrating a commitment to sustainability and environmentally friendly practices that serve as a valuable example. I am also grateful to our keynote and invited speakers, whose insights will guide our discussions and advance progress in the field.

I hope this conference sparks valuable discussions, inspires fresh perspectives, and fosters enduring collaborations. May it serve as a foundation for impactful connections and shared achievements in the field of bioscience.

Thank you.

Faculty of Science Map

1. Faculty of Science Administration
2. Pumpkin Building
3. Pre-clinic Building (PR)
4. Chemistry Building
5. Computer Science Building (CS)
6. Mathematics & Statistics Building (M)
7. Physics Building
8. Biology Building
9. Laboratory Animals Service Center
10. Multiple Laboratory (ML)
11. New Multiple Laboratory (NML)
12. Science & Technology Building
13. Princess Maha Chakri Sirindhorn Natural History Museum

14. Measurement and Standard Accreditation Center

15. Basic Science & Laboratory Building (BSc) : IBSC2024'S Venue

16. Learning Resource Center Building (LRC)
17. Faculty of Nursing
18. Faculty of Dentistry
19. Office of Digital Innovation and Intelligent Systems (DIIS)
20. Sport Complex
21. Faculty of Engineering

**Faculty of Science,
Prince of Songkla University**

SCIENTIFIC PROGRAM

SCIENTIFIC PROGRAM

Date	Time	Activities				
04/28/2024	08:30-09:00	REGISTRATION				
	09:00-09:20	OPENING CEREMONY Prof. Dr. Anchana Prathep Dean of the Faculty of Sciences, Prince of Songkla University, Thailand Prof. Dr. Srdan Rontčević Dean of the Faculty of Sciences, University of Novi Sad, Serbia Asst. Prof. Dr. Niwat Keawpradub President of Prince of Songkla University, Thailand				
	09:20-10:05	PHOTO SESSION KEYNOTE SESSION 1 KN1 : Prof. Dr. Chatchai Muamprasat Faculty of Medicine, Ramathibodi Hospital, Mahidol University, Thailand Coordinator of BCG Frontier Research Cluster, PMU-B "Exploring Frontiers in Bioscience Research"				
	10:50-10:50	KEYNOTE SESSION 2 KN2: Asst. Prof. Dr. Sara Bumrungrasi Biology, Division of Biological Science, Prince of Songkla University "Bioscience Innovations for a Sustainable Tomorrow"				
	10:50-11:15	COFFEE BREAK				
	11:15-12:00	KEYNOTE SESSION 3 KN3 : Prof. Dr. Snežana Malletić Department of Chemistry, Biochemistry and Environmental Protection, Faculty of Sciences, University of Novi Sad, Serbia "Organic Soil Amendments: Pollution Solution or Environmental Risk"				
	12:00-13:00	LUNCH				
			BSC0305 Track 1: Biology/Environment and Climate Change			
	13:00-13:30	INVITED LECTURE INV1-T1 Prof. Dr. Bojana Bokić Department of Biology and Ecology, Faculty of Sciences, University of Novi Sad, Serbia "Traditional use of mints in SE Europe"	BSC0306 Track 2: Biotechnology, Biochemistry and Functional Food INV2-T2 Prof. Dr. Danijela Arsenov Department of Biology and Ecology, Faculty of Sciences, University of Novi Sad, Serbia "Beyond Simple Food—Unveiling the Medicinal Benefits and Human Health Risks of Apiaceae Species"	BSC0307 Track 3: Bioactive Natural Products and Biomedicine Track 1: Biology/Environment and Climate Change INV3-T3 Dr. Muhammad Danial Bin Che Ramli Management and Science University, Malaysia "From Forest to Pharma: The Potential Effects of Natural Products in Neurological Disorder"	BSC0308 Track 4: Bio-sensing Technology and Data Science Track 1: Biology, Environment and Climate Change INV4-T4 Assoc. Prof. Dr. Purim Jarujamrus Department of Chemistry, Faculty of Science, Ubon Ratchathani University "Tailored Functional Nanomaterials as Peroxidase Mimics on Microfluidic Paper-Based Analytical Devices (µPADs) for Innovative Point-of-Care Applications"	BSC0304 Poster Session
	13:30-17:00	Oral Presentation & Poster Presentation	OR2-01 Dr. Nemanja Teslić Green solutions for recovery of secondary metabolites compounds	OR3-01 Assoc. Prof. Dr. Fazia Adyani Ahmad Fuad Exploring the Potential of Chitin and Its Derivative in Inhibiting the Human Hexokinase Isoform 2 Towards Developing Anti-Dengue Drugs	OR4-01 Mr. Preedrag Lugomaja A Decade of Crop Monitoring Through Remote Sensing: Insights into Climate Change Impacts on crop practice, case studies Vojvodina from 2013-2023	Poster Presentation
13:30-13:50	Oral Presentation OR1-01 Assoc. Prof. Dr. Viviana Maresca Pilot study on the use of two different environmental pollution bioindicators, moss and bee, in an area with a high cancer incidence	OR2-02 Dr. Thunchanok Yaikhan Genomic Characterization and Phylogenetic Analysis of <i>Enterocloster aldenensis</i> PSU25A: An Opportunistic Pathogen in Southern Thailand	OR3-02 Ms. Piyyapat Aiemcharoen Biological Activities of Ethanolic Extracts From the Inflorescence of Klauai Namwa (<i>Musa ABB CV</i> , "Klulai Namwa")	OR4-03 Dr. Atchana Lomae Smartphone-enabled electrochemical point-of-care testing for SARS-CoV-2 detection		
13:50-14:10	Oral Presentation OR1-02 Dr. Milica Stankovic From student exchange to climate change					

SCIENTIFIC PROGRAM

Date	Time	Activities
Oct 29, 2024	09:00-09:40	KEYNOTE SESSION 4 KN4: Assoc. Prof. Dr. Surapong Chatpun Department of Biomedical Sciences and Biomedical Engineering, Faculty of Medicine, Prince of Songkla University "Sharing Experience with Staff Exchange in Horizon Europe Framework Programme (HORIZON)"
	09:40-10:20	INVITED SESSION 5 INV5: Ms. Gordana Vlahovic Head of International Relations, Faculty of Sciences, University of Novi Sad, Serbia "Horizon Europe Funding Opportunities: Guidelines for Application"
	10:20-10:40	COFFEE BREAK
	10:40-11:20	INVITED SESSION 6 INV6: Ms. Khobkhai Iniam Program Officer, EU Delegation to Thailand "Erasmus+ Capacity Building in Higher Education: opportunities for universities and staff"
	11:20-12:00	INVITED SESSION 7 INV7: Ms. Ivana Pejovic International Relations Officer, Faculty of Sciences, University of Novi Sad, Serbia "EU/Erasmus+ projects: How to get involved?"
	12:00-13:30	LUNCH
	13:30-15:00	PANEL DISCUSSION SESSION
	13:30-14:30	GROUP DISCUSSION Group 1: Excellent Science & Dual degree for graduate studies and From Lab to Market Facilitator: Assoc. Prof. Dr. Pimonsri Mittraparp-arthorn
		Group 2: Global Challenges (Health, Food, Bioeconomy) and From Lab to Market Facilitator: Assoc. Prof. Dr. Decha Sermwitayawong
		Group 3: Global Challenges (Climate, Natural Resources, Agriculture & Environment) and From Lab to Market Facilitator: Prof. Dr. Anchana Prathep
	14:30-15:00	COFFEE BREAK & WRAP-UP PANEL DISCUSSION (10 minute/Group)

KEYNOTE SPEAKER

Keynote Session 3

Organic Soil Amendments: Pollution Solution or Environmental Risk

Snežana Maletić^{1,*}, Srdan Rončević¹, Jelena Beljin¹, and Marijana Kragulj Isakovski¹

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Abstract: Globally valuable resources are continuously lost through waste streams. Therein, carbon-based wastes such as biomass residues and biosolids can emit substantial amounts of greenhouse gases if landfilled or burned off. Thus, strategies to utilize these resources following concepts of circular economy are urgently needed. One promising approach is converting these resources into valuable organic soil amendments (OSA). Application of organics OSA is a widespread practice worldwide expected to grow in use and application scenarios. OSA can play a key role in maintaining soil functioning and facilitating a shift towards a resource-efficient, low-carbon, and climate-resilient agro-economy by minimizing the environmental footprint of agricultural food production. An important aspect of OSA application is that these amendments can be a source and/or a sink of nutrients as well as organic and inorganic pollutants (pharmaceuticals, pesticides, heavy metals etc.). Thus, they are expected to affect soil subsurface and groundwater contamination. Due to the many direct and indirect interactions of organic matter in the complex soil system, numerous processes relevant to nutrient and contaminant dynamics are affected by the application of OSA. Important processes include stabilizing effect for transport, increased solubility of some organic compounds, competition for sorption sites, complexation of metals, and soil organic matter-mineral interactions. Additionally, different OSA are highly variable, with some of them potentially releasing harmful substances. Furthermore, experimental conditions in the lab and field, different soil types, different crops, climate zones, and agricultural management strategies lead to many possible conditions in the soil. This makes a generalizable assessment of OSA effect on sorption, transformation and transport processes in soil challenging. This presentation explores the dual role of organic soil amendments as beneficial soil enhancers and potential environmental risks. Through a review of selected studies, we will highlight the pathways through which these contaminants can enter the soil and their impact on plant health, and soil ecosystems.

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